

RDM Planning Maturity Assessment Tool (MAT) for Australian Research Institutions

An implementation project for the Institutional Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

University of Technology Sydney

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About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

University of Technology Sydney (UTS) has developed a maturity assessment tool (MAT) to evaluate the effectiveness of its current research data management (RDM) Planning practices. The tool was based primarily on the [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#), in particular the 19 recommendations arising from the RDM Planning element. These recommendations were used as a benchmark to assess how well UTS was meeting its RDM requirements (as outlined in documents such as the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research (the Code) and the Management of Data and Information in Research guide supporting the Code), but to also evaluate its practices against sector-wide expectations around RDM planning practices.

The recommendations are ideal for this approach, given how the framework was developed with the expertise and experience of representatives from an array of research institutions across Australia.

The project involved several stages:

1. Environment scan for similar tools — Including ARDC's FAIR self-assessment tool, NSW State Archives and Records' Records Management Assessment Tool (RMAT), and, though not an assessment tool, the RISE Workshop material.
2. Design and development — The MAT was designed to assess an institution's maturity against 19 recommendations of the RDM Planning Framework Element.
3. Review by Project Team — Drawing on collective expertise from across an array of support units, the MAT was reviewed to ensure it effectively unpacked the recommendations in clear, understandable questions, and presented this content in an accessible format.
4. Independent testing — Conducted internally by a panel of representatives from eResearch, Research Integrity, Library and Faculty Administration, and an external review by Federation University to ensure the MAT met its aims as a broad scale, multi-stakeholder assessment of an institution's RDM Planning practices.
5. Refine and final review — The MAT was refined into its final iteration in accordance with the feedback from both testing panels.

Resulting Improvements

The key improvement has been engendering greater engagement with stakeholders from across the university, broader than the array of RDM expertise at the project team level. This not only allowed us to leverage expertise from a range of units in support of the project, but to identify and enlist key stakeholders involved in RDM Planning moving forward, ensuring future decisions have a wide array of input. cursory use of the MAT during the development and testing phase has already identified gaps in our RDM Planning maturity that we are incorporating into our planning, coming at a pivotal time as we

move into the 2023 funding cycle. For example, this exercise has laid the groundwork for refining our RDM Services RACI, as well as identified specific projects that require attention going forward.

Next Steps

The primary aim of the next phase is to find a suitable method for sharing the MAT with the sector, ensuring it is accessible for, and relevant to, all interested institutions. The other aim is to use the MAT to conduct a full maturity assessment for UTS. The testing phase has provided snapshots of current practices, successes and deficits, but the next step will be a full assessment, utilising the stakeholder engagement during the project development and testing phases.

This will have several results:

1. Full utilisation of the MAT for its intended purpose for UTS
2. Inform priorities for RDM Planning development activities
3. Provide evidence for reporting to university management to secure resources for identified RDM development projects.

This process will also inform greater refinement of the MAT itself, with the plan for newer iterations of the MAT in the future. UTS intends to share the outcomes of the full assessment with other interested institutions.

Project Outputs

Mertin, A., Wheeler, L., Tampubolon, P., Naray, D., Su, S., Hamblett, R., Chan, H., Salahuddin, H., Loxton, D., Litting, D., & Liu, L. (W. (2022). Institutional Research Data Management (RDM) Planning Maturity Assessment Tool (MAT). University of Technology Sydney. <https://doi.org/10.26195/XV24-CR59>

The RDM Planning MAT is available through the UTS Data Portal. It is presented as a single Excel workbook, with 7 sheets that can be viewed as three sections:

- Front matter and supporting material (sheets 1, 2, 7), comprising
 - How to use this document
 - IRDM for Institutions Framework Recommendations
 - Glossary
- Assessment sheets, divided into three sections
 - Governance
 - Culture and Support
 - Infrastructure

- Assessment Summary

The MAT is presented in this self-contained manner to aid and simplify use, however, the process by which the MAT will be utilised will require additional documentation and planning by an institution. This is briefly outlined in the “How to use this document” sheet to aid an institution in planning its maturity assessment. It is envisaged that this MAT would be of benefit to institutions of varying maturity, and can be utilised in future whenever there may be changes in regulation, legislation, or even internal policy revisions that cut across research, and specifically RDM Planning.

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).